

Economic and Social Deficiency: Their Influence on Students Academic Performance

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Abstract

This study ascertained to find out relationship between economic and social deficiency and their influence on education students' academic performance at West Visayas State University-Janiuay Campus, School Year 2014-2015. The descriptive-correlational method was used with academic performance as dependent variable and economic and social deficiency as independent variables. The participants were the 266 students selected through stratified random sampling. Data were gathered through questionnaire-checklist and Grade Point Average. The statistical tools used were frequency, rank, mean, standard deviation, and Pearson's r computed through SPSS. The results show that the top three predominant economic deficiencies are inability to join in school activities; inability to pay for photocopy of hand outs and other reference materials; inability to spend any amount for snacks/lunch. Likewise, the top three most social deficiencies are understanding community norms; having social perception, making choices and self-monitoring; perceiving how others are feeling and sharing empathy. Further, education students have a "moderate extent" social deficiency and the overall performance was "very good". Moreover, a negative correlation but no significant relationship existed between economic and social deficiency and between social deficiency and academic performance. The economic deficiency and academic performance revealed a positive and no significant relationship.

Keywords: Academic performance; Economic deficiency; Social deficiency.

Introduction

Students are considered to be the center of an educative process. They are the most essential asset in an educational institution. With this, they are the ones giving worth to schools, colleges and universities. The development of the country both in social and economic would always depend on the academic performance of the student. This is because the students' performance would pave the way on producing quality graduates who are capable of becoming a leader and manpower for the country (Ali et.al, 2009). Social, psychological, economic, environmental and personal factors may influence students' performance which also varies from person to person or country to country.

The School of Teacher Education students mostly came from low income families. Some of them resorted to being a student assistant to compensate their school needs such as tuition fees and allowances. Also, some of them look for private individuals to finance their educational needs as a return of their services rendered as personal assistant or being a helper at home. Social deficiencies were also observed from them because there are some students who are inactive in some school activities due to lack of financial support and/or low self-esteem. Their lack of participation in some school activities hinders their personality development and self-growth as an individual.

The study may helpful for both policy makers of the university and parents of the students. It helps the college administration to design to achieve quality education and implement the policies to improve the students' performance and the quality of education by changing the outlook of students towards education. In addition, the study would not only assist the university to improve the level of performance of teacher education students, but it would also provide strategies to guide the educators to improve the performance of learners - to be globally competitive. Parents can use the findings of the study to solve the problems of students especially the financial problems and find ways to look after them. It may also generate awareness among students about their rights and responsibilities to attain quality education.

The schematic representation of the study is shown below:

Figure1: Schematic Diagram of the Hypothetical Relationships Among the Economic and Social Deficiencies and Students Academic Performance.

Review of Literature

Adams (1996), presented that children from families with low socioeconomic status face problems when they attend schools. The result of the study showed that socioeconomic status (SES) is closely related to income and educational level. Indeed, socioeconomic status is one of the most researched and debated factors among educational professionals which study the academic performance of students. It is believed to affect the quality of the academic performance of the students. Most of the experts said that if the basic needs of the students are unfulfilled, they could not perform better academically. Thus, low socioeconomic has a negative effect on the academic performance of the students. The US Department of Education (2003), reported that the low self-esteem of students is the result of environmental deficiencies caused by socioeconomic status.

Above and beyond the other demographic factors, the effects of SES are still prevalent at the individual level (Capraro, M., Capraro, R., & Wiggins, 2000). The SES can be deliberated in a number of different ways; it is most often calculated by looking at parental education, occupation, income, and facilities used by individuals separately or collectively. Parental education and family SES level have positive correlations with the student's quality of achievement (Caldas & Bankston, 1997; Jeynes, 2002; Parelius, D., & Parelius, A., 1987; Mitchell & Collom, 2001; Ma & Klinger, 2000). The students with high level of SES perform better than the middle class students and the middle class students perform better than the students with low level of SES (Garzon, 2006; Kahlenberg, 2006; Kirkup, 2008).

In the study of Mc Neal (2001) cited by by Mahmood Shah, Aamir Atta, Muhammad Imran Qureshi & Humaira Shah (2012) found out that SES has the greatest influence compared to other educational influences such as family size, parental involvements and educational level of the parents. Jeynes (2002) reported that there is a positive correlation between SES of a family and the academic achievements of a student. In addition, Hochschild (2003) said that students earn lower test score and are likely to drop out of school because they belong to low SES. Likewise, Eamon (2005) believed that low SES negatively affects academic achievements because low SES prevents access to vital resources and creates additional stress at home.

Statement of the Problem

This study sought to find out the economic and social deficiencies and its influence on students' academic performance. Specifically, this study sought answers to the economic social deficiencies experienced by teacher education students, the extent does the social deficiency influence the teacher education students, the academic performance of students as influence by economic and social deficiencies, and if there significant relationships among economic and social deficiencies and academic performance of students. Likewise, the hypothesis advanced in this study was there are no significant relationships among economic and social deficiencies and academic performance of students.

Research Methodology

This study was conducted to determine the forms of economic and social deficiencies and its relationships to students' academic performance. The descriptive-correlational method of research was employed in the study. According to Gay (2002), the descriptive method of research involves collecting data to answer questions concerning the current status of the subject under study.

The participants of the study were the two-hundred sixty-six (266) teacher education students enrolled in Bachelor of Elementary Education and Bachelor of Secondary Education for the Second Semester, School Year 2014-2015. These numbers of students were taken from first year to fourth year college of West Visayas State University-Janiuay Campus. The sample size was proportionately distributed among teacher education students in different year level and degree program. In determining the sample size, the researchers used the Slovin's Formula, (Pagoso, et al. 1987). Lastly, the researchers employed stratified random sampling method through lottery.

The independent variables are the economic and social deficiencies, and the dependent variable is students' academic performance. The data gathering instruments were researcher-constructed questionnaire-checklist and the GPA of students from the office of the registrar. Similarly, data were analyzed through, rank, mean, standard deviation and Pearson's r at .05 level of significance.

The given scale was used to interpret the results of the data gathered on the extent of social deficiency: 3.67 – 5.00: High extent; 2.34 – 3.66: Moderate extent; and 1.00 – 2.33: Slight Extent.

The given scale was used to interpret the result of academic performance of the respondents: 1.24 – 1.00 Excellent; 1.49– 1.25: Highly Outstanding; 1.74 – 1.50: Outstanding; 1.99 - 1.75: Very Good; 2.24 - 2.00: Good; 2.49 - 2.25: Very Satisfactory; 2.74 - 2.50: Satisfactory; 2.99 - 2.75: Fair; 3.00: Passing; and 5.00: Failure.

Findings and Interpretation

Economic Deficiencies Experienced by Teacher Education Students

Data in Table 1 indicate that the most predominant economic deficiencies experienced by teacher education students. The results show that the top five (5) predominant economic deficiencies are as follows: Inability to join in any school activities; inability to pay for photocopy of hand outs and other reference materials; inability to spend any amount for snacks/lunch; inability to pay materials for projects/research outputs; and inability to pay contribution for extracurricular activities.

The results of this study upheld the statement of Thompson and Fleming (2003) which states that provision and availability of extra learning facilities made the children from high and middle economic status families to have a better exposure to learning at home. In addition, students who are provided with computer facilities both at home and at school achieved a significantly higher science score than those who only used computer at school. With this, it was believed that family possessions are connected to economic status of the students which eventually affected their scores. Children belonging to low socioeconomic status have limited or do not have access to additional facilities that aid for their learning, thus, their opportunity to get to the top of their educational ladder may be difficult.

In general, deficiency in financial aspects towards their studies was identified among teacher education students. Also, their daily allowance to keep up with the high cost of living is not enough. Teacher education students' allowance is too low. With this, they were deprived from joining campus activities, photocopying of handouts and buying snacks. This shows from having difficulty in getting out from the sad situation.

Table 1: Economic Deficiencies Experienced By Teacher Education Students

Item	Mean	Rank
Inability to join to join in any school activities	2.54	1
Inability to pay for photocopy of hand outs and other reference materials	2.46	2
Inability to spend any amount for snacks/lunch	2.34	3
Inability to pay materials for projects/research outputs	2.33	4
Inability to pay contribution for extracurricular activities	2.30	5
Inability to buy school supplies for your studies	2.21	6
Inability to pay tuition and miscellaneous fees	2.17	7.5
Inability to pay membership fees of school organization and minor organizations	2.17	7.5
Inability to pay for transportation service	1.90	9
Inability to pay the rent for boarding house	1.55	10

Social Deficiencies Experienced by Teacher Education Students

Results in Table 2 revealed that of the 20 items, the top five most social deficiencies experienced by teacher education students are as follows: understanding community norms; having social perception, making choices and self-monitoring; perceiving how others are feeling and sharing empathy; having determine behavior for different social situation; and having appropriate topics for conversation with the mean ranging from 3.16 – 3.43. On the other hand, results revealed that only one item has the mean of 1.42 (flirting).

One of the factors that play a crucial role in the academic potential of the children is environment. Goddard (2003), presented that the academic success and personal characteristics of individuals are directly related to each other. In terms of students' academic accomplishments, members of schools and families/communities are also believed to have played a vital role. The academic success of the students may be influence by social assistance a student received from his/her various support groups. Students' academic performance was assisted by many forms of social support which students may have access to. Relational trust and positive support groups which are examples of relational networks and social features are also believed to be essential. According to Goddard (2003), relationships that have little trust and are discouraging positive academic performance r are detrimental for student success. Further, Goddard (2003) argued that academic successes of the children are influenced by factors such as social structure that involves parents, children and community.

Data obtained from the study supported the research on poor academic performance (Saiduddin, 2003). The study revealed that poverty, cultural differences, unstable homes, drug abuse and teenage pregnancy are among of the factors that affect poor academic performance. Poor performance an learners dropping out were identified to be the effect of exposure of the youth to negative role models from an early age. Therefore, research results revealed that children came from intact homes was unlikely to repeat a school grade though socioeconomic status was removed statistically.

Table 2: Social Deficiencies Experienced by Teacher Education Students

Item	Mean	Rank
Understanding community norms	3.43	1.5
Having social perception, making choices and self- monitoring	3.43	1.5
Perceiving how others are feeling and sharing empathy	3.37	3
Having determine behavior for different social situation	3.21	4
Having appropriate topics for conversation	3.16	5
Having determine whether someone is trustworthy	3.14	6
Having ability to maintain appropriate personal space	3.08	7
Ability to interact to others with authority figures	2.89	8
Ability to shake hands when meeting someone	2.79	9
Inability to recognize/identify the feelings of others	2.54	10
Having depression, anxiety, or hyperactivity	2.49	11
Having inability to maintain eye contact with other during conversation	2.43	12
Inability to use the right tone and volume of voice	2.42	13
Inability to use appropriate emotional response to others	2.40	14
Inability to express opinions to others	2.39	15
Inability to smile when greeting people	2.36	16
Inability to resolve conflicts and taking turns	2.35	17
Inability to understand and decode gestures/body language and facial expression	2.31	18
Inability to begin and end conversation	2.27	19
Flirting	1.42	20

The Extent of Social Deficiencies of Teacher Education Students

Data in Table 3 indicate that of the 22 items in social deficiency, only three items got the results of “slight extent” with the mean ranging from 1.42 – 2.31. These items are as follows: inability to understand and decode gestures/body language and facial expression; inability to begin and end conversation; and flirting. In addition, the rest of the items have a “moderate extent” of social deficiency with the mean ranging from 2.34 – 3.66. On the other hand, the result revealed that none of the item got a “high extent”. Generally, teacher education students have a “moderate extent” (M = 2.69; SD = .96) social deficiency.

Goddard (2003) reported that academic success of individuals and personal characteristics are directly related to each other. In terms of students’ academic accomplishments, members of schools and families/communities are also believed to have played a vital role. The academic performance of the students was assisted by the many forms of social support they get. Their academic success was affected by social assistant a student received from his/her various support groups. In addition, relational trust and positive support groups which are examples of relational networks and social features are also considered essential. Relationships that have little trust and are discouraging positive academic performance are detrimental for student success.

Table 3: The Extent of Social Deficiencies of Teacher Education Students

Item	Mean	Description	SD
Having inability to maintain eye contact with other during conversation	2.43	Moderate extent	.99
Having ability to maintain appropriate personal space	3.08	Moderate extent	.95
Inability to understand and decode gestures/body language and facial expression	2.31	Slight extent	.86
Inability to resolve conflicts and taking turns	2.35	Moderate extent	.75
Inability to begin and end conversation	2.27	Slight extent	.89
Having appropriate topics for conversation	3.16	Moderate extent	.86
Ability to interact to others with authority figures	2.89	Moderate extent	.96
Inability to smile when greeting people	2.36	Moderate extent	1.37
Ability to shake hands when meeting someone	2.79	Moderate extent	1.07
Inability to use the right tone and volume of voice	2.42	Moderate extent	1.05
Flirting	1.42	Slight extent	.76
Inability to express opinions to others	2.39	Moderate extent	.96
Inability to use appropriate emotional response to others	2.40	Moderate extent	.93
Inability to recognize/identify the feelings of others	2.54	Moderate extent	.98
Having determine whether someone is trustworthy	3.14	Moderate extent	.94
Having determine behavior for different social situation	3.21	Moderate extent	.91
Understanding community norms	3.43	Moderate extent	.95
Having social perception, making choices and self- monitoring	3.43	Moderate extent	.97
Having depression, anxiety, or hyperactivity	2.49	Moderate extent	.96
Perceiving how others are feeling and sharing empathy	3.37	Moderate extent	1.01
Overall Mean	2.69	Moderate extent	0.96

Academic Performance of Teacher Education Students as Influence by Economic and Social Deficiencies

Table 4 shows that the academic performance of first year BEED and BSED teacher education students was good. Likewise, the second year BEED and BSED teacher education students got a very good performance towards their studies. Further, the performance of third BEED students showed a good performance, while the BSED students perform better than the BEED with a very good rating. Lastly, the fourth year BEED and BSED teacher education students got a high outstanding performance in their studies. Generally, the overall performance of teacher education students was “very good” (M = 1.96; SD = .35). These results are based on the official records of teacher education students from the office of the registrar.

This result conforms to the study by M.S. Farooq, A.H. Chaudhry, M. Shafiq, G. Berhanu (2011). It was found out that socio-economic status and parent’s education have significant effect on students’ overall academic achievement and achievement in mathematics and English. The high and average level of socio-economic affect the performance more than the lower level. It was also found out that education has a greater impact to their children’s academic performance than their occupation. Also, the girls perform better than male students. Secker, 2004 in Blevins (2009), said that students from a high socio-economic status perform better than those from low socio-economic status when groups of students with similar backgrounds are compared. Fewer discipline problems and higher social expectations are related to high socio-economic status.

Heyneman, 2005 as cited by Blevins (2009), stated that effective performance in school was not shown by the students from low socio-economic background. It is not also necessarily true that social status is the key factor in academic

performance. Other factors were identified but not limited to subject, student's age, and gender. The integration of social classes among schools is the important solution as Heyneman concluded. There must also be a shift from choosing the gap of social status of adults to the integration of the social classes.

GPA		Mean	Description	SD
First	BEED	2.20	Good	.23
	BSED	2.20	Good	.18
Second	BEED	1.98	Very Good	.20
	BSED	1.94	Very Good	.27
Third	BEED	2.09	Good	.24
	BSED	1.85	Very Good	.16
Fourth	BEED	1.29	Highly Outstanding	.14
	BSED	1.46	Highly Outstanding	.14
Overall Mean		1.96	Very Good	.35

Relationships among Economic and Social Deficiencies and Academic Performance of Education Students

Based on the results in Table 5, negative correlation but no significant relationship existed between economic deficiency and social deficiency. Likewise, the economic deficiency and academic performance of teacher education students revealed a positive correlation and no significant relationship existed. Lastly, between social deficiency and academic performance of students has a negative correlation but no significant relationship existed. Therefore, the null hypothesis advanced in this study is accepted. Further, the results showed that the computed r value is higher than alpha level of significance, thus, the economic deficiency and social deficiency, economic deficiency and academic performance, as well as social and academic performance do not influence from each other.

The result of the study supported the study by by Mahmood Shah, Aamir Atta, Muhammad Imran Qureshi & Humaira Shah (2012), which revealed that there is a positive and strong correlation between socio-economic status and academic achievements of the children. Likewise, it also favored the study conducted by Jeynes (2002) which revealed that there is a positive correlation between socio-economic status and academic achievement of a student. Moreover, Hochschild (2003) said that students earn lower test results and more likely to drop out of school because of low socio-economic status. Eamon (2005), also believed that low socio-economic status prevents access to vital resources and creates additional stress at home, thus, socio-economic status gives negative effects on academic achievements of the students. In contrast, a negative relationship between the family income and students' performance was the findings of the study by Hijaz and Naqvi (2006). It was also found out by these researchers that they focus on the private college.

Variables	r- value	p- value	Remarks	Decision
Economic Deficiency and Social Deficiency	-.13	.71	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Economic Deficiency and Academic Performance	.17	.64	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Social Deficiency and Academic Performance	-.12	.62	Not Significant	Accept Ho
alpha = .05 level of significance				

Conclusions

The Teacher Education students of West Visayas State University – Janiway Campus were affected by the economic deficiencies. They were struggling hard in order to survive. Moreover, the students were economically deprived and most often unable to make both ends meet. The teacher education students were having difficulty in understanding community norms. In addition, they were having difficulty in social perception and making choices for themselves. They also suffer from complexity in different social situations in the community. Likewise, they were often out of the topics in dealing with conversation with others. Despite the experienced economic and social deficiencies, students still perform well towards their studies. They are still dedicated and committed in performing their duties and responsibilities as a student. They seem to have maximized their effort towards their chosen course. Further, they seem to accomplish their work and are committed to do it in order to finish a degree. Moreover, there was a weak correlation between economic and social deficiencies and between social deficiency and academic performance of students. On the contrary, economic deficiency and academic performance of students have strong correlation.

Recommendations

The administration should provide proper leaning facilities to the students and also improve the environment of the campus and encourage the faculty to reduce the demand from the students due to a high cost of outputs/projects. In addition, the administration should design and implement the policies to improve the students' performance and the quality of education by changing the attitude of students towards learning, facilitating students and improving the teaching procedures.

It is recommended that government should increase allocation of funds to provide for more amenities to facilitate learning in the schools and economic empowerment program should be embarked on to enhance parent's income. Likewise, the student organizations should subsidize the extracurricular activities for the students to participate chargeable against membership fee.

Parents and teachers should provide proper guidance to the students in order to perform well toward their studies. They should provide series of lectures, seminars and counseling among students and expose them through participation in various campus activities. These activities require proper training, organizational planning and skills to conduct such studies for determining the contributing factors inside and outside school. This process of identification of variables must be given full attention and priority so that the teachers may be able to develop instructional strategies for making sure that all the children be provided with the opportunities to arrive at their fullest potential in learning and performance. Further research is needed to explore the problem on a large sample from more scattered geographical regions including other student factors, family factors, school factors and peer factors.

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